

Kaggle: Nigerians in Data Science

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Author: [Alao David I.](#)

0.1 This is a Notebook Exploring Data on Nigerian Data Scientists

0.1.1 Introduction: Nigeria is the most populous country in Africa, and 7th in the World, just behind Brazil which is 9 times bigger in landmass.

Around [2.64% of the World's Population is Nigerian](#) and **2.7% of Kaggle Data Scientists are Nigerian**, with the country's youthful population even more than the entire population of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland.

*The frontline is ever expanding in the technological sphere, [Data is the New Oil](#), and [technological advancements have been proven to be a major driver of economic development](#), hence, this is **definitely a great time for Nigerians to get in and innovate.***

0.1.2 Aim: *The Aim of this Analytic endeavour is to highlight certain facts and figures about Data Scientists in Nigeria, as well as, making certain predictions on what the future holds...*

0.1.3 Setting up the environment

```
[1]: import numpy as np, pandas as pd
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression

from fbprophet import Prophet
import os, sys
import warnings
warnings.simplefilter('ignore')
```

```
[2]: path = '../input/kaggle-survey-2021/'
print('Datasets')
os.listdir(path)
```

Datasets

```
[2]: ['kaggle_survey_2021_responses.csv', 'supplementary_data']
```

0.1.4 Accessing the Dataset and Data Pre-processing

```
[3]: raw_df = pd.read_csv(path + 'kaggle_survey_2021_responses.csv')
raw_df.head()
```

```
[3]: Time from Start to Finish (seconds)          Q1 \
0          Duration (in seconds)  What is your age (# years)?
1                                910          50-54
2                                784          50-54
3                                924          22-24
4                                575          45-49
```

```
                                Q2 \
0  What is your gender? - Selected Choice
1                                Man
2                                Man
3                                Man
4                                Man
```

```
                                Q3 \
0  In which country do you currently reside?
1                                India
2                                Indonesia
3                                Pakistan
4                                Mexico
```

```
                                Q4 \
0  What is the highest level of formal education ...
1                                Bachelor's degree
2                                Master's degree
3                                Master's degree
4                                Doctoral degree
```

```
                                Q5 \
0  Select the title most similar to your current ...
1                                Other
2                                Program/Project Manager
3                                Software Engineer
4                                Research Scientist
```

```
                                Q6 \
0  For how many years have you been writing code ...
1                                5-10 years
2                                20+ years
3                                1-3 years
4                                20+ years
```

```

                                Q7_Part_1 \
0 What programming languages do you use on a reg...
1                                Python
2                                NaN
3                                Python
4                                Python

```

```

                                Q7_Part_2 \
0 What programming languages do you use on a reg...
1                                R
2                                NaN
3                                NaN
4                                NaN

```

```

                                Q7_Part_3 ... \
0 What programming languages do you use on a reg... ...
1                                NaN ...
2                                SQL ...
3                                NaN ...
4                                NaN ...

```

```

                                Q38_B_Part_3 \
0 In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...
1                                NaN
2                                NaN
3                                NaN
4                                NaN

```

```

                                Q38_B_Part_4 \
0 In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...
1                                NaN
2                                NaN
3                                NaN
4                                NaN

```

```

                                Q38_B_Part_5 \
0 In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...
1                                NaN
2                                NaN
3                                TensorBoard
4                                NaN

```

```

                                Q38_B_Part_6 \
0 In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...
1                                NaN
2                                NaN
3                                NaN

```

4		NaN
		Q38_B_Part_7 \
0	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	
1		NaN
2		NaN
3		NaN
4		NaN
		Q38_B_Part_8 \
0	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	
1		NaN
2		NaN
3		NaN
4		NaN
		Q38_B_Part_9 \
0	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	
1		NaN
2		NaN
3		NaN
4		NaN
		Q38_B_Part_10 \
0	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	
1		NaN
2		NaN
3		NaN
4		NaN
		Q38_B_Part_11 \
0	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	
1		NaN
2		None
3		NaN
4		None
		Q38_B_OTHER
0	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	
1		NaN
2		NaN
3		NaN
4		NaN

[5 rows x 369 columns]

```
[4]: #Map columns to actual question asked
print('Map columns to actual question asked', end ='\n\n')
cols = pd.DataFrame(raw_df.columns)
raw_df.iloc[:1]
```

Map columns to actual question asked

```
[4]: Time from Start to Finish (seconds)          Q1 \
0          Duration (in seconds)  What is your age (# years)?

          Q2 \
0  What is your gender? - Selected Choice

          Q3 \
0  In which country do you currently reside?

          Q4 \
0  What is the highest level of formal education ...

          Q5 \
0  Select the title most similar to your current ...

          Q6 \
0  For how many years have you been writing code ...

          Q7_Part_1 \
0  What programming languages do you use on a reg...

          Q7_Part_2 \
0  What programming languages do you use on a reg...

          Q7_Part_3 ... \
0  What programming languages do you use on a reg... ...

          Q38_B_Part_3 \
0  In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...

          Q38_B_Part_4 \
0  In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...

          Q38_B_Part_5 \
0  In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...

          Q38_B_Part_6 \
0  In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...
```

```

                                Q38_B_Part_7 \
0 In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...

                                Q38_B_Part_8 \
0 In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...

                                Q38_B_Part_9 \
0 In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...

                                Q38_B_Part_10 \
0 In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...

                                Q38_B_Part_11 \
0 In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...

                                Q38_B_OTHER
0 In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...

```

[1 rows x 369 columns]

```
[5]: df = raw_df.drop(0, axis = 0)
```

```
[6]: mask = df['Q3'] == 'Nigeria'      #df['Q3'] == 'In which country do you
      ↪currently reside?'
      NGA = df[mask]
      print('Nigeria-specific Dataset - NGA\n')
      NGA.head(1)
```

Nigeria-specific Dataset - NGA

```
[6]:
Time from Start to Finish (seconds)    Q1    Q2    Q3    Q4 \
14                                     852  45-49  Man  Nigeria  Master's degree

                                Q5    Q6  Q7_Part_1  Q7_Part_2  Q7_Part_3  ... \
14 Program/Project Manager  5-10 years  Python    NaN    SQL    ...

      Q38_B_Part_3  Q38_B_Part_4  Q38_B_Part_5  Q38_B_Part_6  Q38_B_Part_7 \
14             NaN             NaN             NaN             NaN             NaN

      Q38_B_Part_8  Q38_B_Part_9  Q38_B_Part_10  Q38_B_Part_11  Q38_B_OTHER
14             NaN             NaN             NaN             NaN             NaN

```

[1 rows x 369 columns]

```
[7]: print ('Columns with missing values - col_mis')
      mis = NGA.isnull().sum()
```

```
col_mis = pd.DataFrame()

col_mis['Questions Asked'] = raw_df[mis[mis>0].index].iloc[0].values
col_mis['Number of Missing Values'] = mis[mis>0].values
col_mis.index = mis[mis>0].index
col_mis.T
```

Columns with missing values - col_mis

```
[7]:
```

		Q7_Part_1 \
Questions Asked	What programming languages do you use on a reg..	
Number of Missing Values		137
		Q7_Part_2 \
Questions Asked	What programming languages do you use on a reg..	
Number of Missing Values		597
		Q7_Part_3 \
Questions Asked	What programming languages do you use on a reg..	
Number of Missing Values		475
		Q7_Part_4 \
Questions Asked	What programming languages do you use on a reg..	
Number of Missing Values		672
		Q7_Part_5 \
Questions Asked	What programming languages do you use on a reg..	
Number of Missing Values		650
		Q7_Part_6 \
Questions Asked	What programming languages do you use on a reg..	
Number of Missing Values		649
		Q7_Part_7 \
Questions Asked	What programming languages do you use on a reg..	
Number of Missing Values		589
		Q7_Part_8 \
Questions Asked	What programming languages do you use on a reg..	
Number of Missing Values		701
		Q7_Part_9 \
Questions Asked	What programming languages do you use on a reg..	
Number of Missing Values		699
		Q7_Part_10 \
Questions Asked	What programming languages do you use on a reg..	

Number of Missing Values		692
Questions Asked	... \	
Number of Missing Values	...	
Questions Asked		Q38_B_Part_3 \
Number of Missing Values	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	669
Questions Asked		Q38_B_Part_4 \
Number of Missing Values	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	662
Questions Asked		Q38_B_Part_5 \
Number of Missing Values	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	507
Questions Asked		Q38_B_Part_6 \
Number of Missing Values	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	657
Questions Asked		Q38_B_Part_7 \
Number of Missing Values	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	662
Questions Asked		Q38_B_Part_8 \
Number of Missing Values	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	643
Questions Asked		Q38_B_Part_9 \
Number of Missing Values	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	666
Questions Asked		Q38_B_Part_10 \
Number of Missing Values	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	549
Questions Asked		Q38_B_Part_11 \
Number of Missing Values	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	644
Questions Asked		Q38_B_OTHER
Number of Missing Values	In the next 2 years, do you hope to become mor...	691

[2 rows x 362 columns]

```
[8]: print ('Decriptive Statistics\n')
      NGA.describe()
```

Decriptive Statistics

```
[8]:      Time from Start to Finish (seconds)      Q1  Q2      Q3  \
count      702      702  702      702
unique      607      9   3       1
top      522  25-29  Man  Nigeria
freq      3     207  594      702

      Q4      Q5      Q6  Q7_Part_1  Q7_Part_2  Q7_Part_3  \
count      702      702      702      565      105      227
unique      7     14      7         1         1         1
top  Bachelor's degree  Student  1-3 years  Python      R      SQL
freq      363      139      269      565      105      227

      ...  Q38_B_Part_3      Q38_B_Part_4  Q38_B_Part_5  Q38_B_Part_6  \
count  ...      33         40         195         45
unique  ...      1         1         1         1
top  ...  Comet.ml  Sacred + Omniboard  TensorBoard  Guild.ai
freq  ...      33         40         195         45

      Q38_B_Part_7  Q38_B_Part_8      Q38_B_Part_9  Q38_B_Part_10  \
count      40         59         36         153
unique      1         1         1         1
top  Polyaxon  ClearML  Domino Model Monitor  MLflow
freq      40         59         36         153

      Q38_B_Part_11  Q38_B_OTHER
count      58         11
unique      1         1
top      None      Other
freq      58         11
```

[4 rows x 369 columns]

0.1.5 Define Necessary Visualization Functions

```
[9]: def label_plot(title = 'Distribution Plot', x = 'X-axis', y = 'Y-axis'):
      plt.title(title, weight = 'bold', fontsize = 17)
      plt.ylabel(y, weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
      plt.xlabel(x, weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
```

```

def plot_bar(dataset, column = None, horizontal = False, figsize = (20,10),
↳color = 'darkcyan'):
    if column == None:
        if horizontal:
            dataset.value_counts().plot.barh(figsize = figsize, color = color)
            plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
        else:
            return dataset.value_counts().plot.bar(figsize = figsize, color =
↳color)
    else:
        if horizontal:
            dataset[column].value_counts().plot.barh(figsize = figsize, color =
↳color)
            plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
        else:
            return dataset[column].value_counts().plot.barh(figsize = figsize,
↳color = color)

def plot_donut(dataset, column = None, title = 'Donut Plot', figsize = (20,10),
↳shadow = False, color = False, explode = False, background = 'white'):

    plt.figure(figsize = figsize)

    if column == None: data = dataset.value_counts()
    else: data = dataset[column].value_counts()
    labs = data.values

    plt.title(title, weight = 'bold', fontsize = 30)

    if not color: color = ['darkcyan', 'green', 'darkorange', 'black',
↳'darkred', 'darkmagenta', 'gold']
    if not explode:
        try: explode = [0] + (list(np.linspace(0.05,0.1, len(labs) - 2))[:-1])
↳+ [0]
        except: explode = [0] * len(labs)

    data.plot.pie(
        label = '',
        colors = color,

```

```

        shadow = shadow,
        explode = explode,
        autopct = lambda x: f'{round(x, 2)}%'

    circle = plt.Circle( (0,0), 0.8, color='white')
    plt.gcf().gca().add_artist(circle)

```

```

def annot_bar(plots):
    for bar in plots.patches:
        plots.annotate(format(bar.get_height(), '.0f'),
                        (bar.get_x() + bar.get_width() / 2,
                         bar.get_height()), ha='center', va='center',
                        size=15, xytext=(0, 8),
                        textcoords='offset points')

```

0.1.6 Exploratory Data Analysis

```

[10]: numNGA, numRES = len(NGA), len(df)
      perNGA = round((numNGA/numRES) *100, 2)
      #print(f'{numNGA}, out of {numRES} respondents are Nigerians')
      #print(f'{perNGA}% of total respondents are Nigerian')

```

```

[11]: #List of African Countries to filter from
      africa = ['Nigeria',
                'Ethiopia',
                'Democratic Republic of the Congo',
                'Egypt',
                'South Africa',
                'Tanzania',
                'Kenya',
                'Uganda',
                'Algeria',
                'Sudan',
                'Morocco',
                'Angola',
                'Ghana',
                'Cameroon',
                'Madagascar',
                'Mozambique',
                'Ivory Coast',
                'Niger',
                'Mali',

```

```

'Burkina Faso',
'Malawi',
'Chad',
'Somalia',
'Zimbabwe',
'Zambia',
'Senegal',
'South Sudan',
'Rwanda',
'Guinea',
'Benin',
'Tunisia',
'Burundi',
'Sierra Leone',
'Togo',
'Libya',
'Eritrea',
'Republic of the Congo',
'Liberia',
'Central African Republic',
'Mauritania',
'Gambia',
'Botswana',
'Gabon',
'Namibia',
'Lesotho',
'Guinea-Bissau',
'Mauritius',
'Equatorial Guinea',
'Eswatini',
'Djibouti',
'Réunion',
'Comoros',
'Cape Verde',
'Western Sahara',
'Mayotte',
'São Tomé and Príncipe',
'Seychelles',
'Saint Helena, Ascension and Tristan da Cunha']

```

```

[12]: uniq1 = df['Q3'].drop(df['Q3'][df['Q3'].str.contains('Other')].index, axis = 0)
      uniq = uniq1.replace('United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland',
      ↪ ↪ 'United Kingdom').value_counts()

african, others = {}, {}
for country, pop in zip(uniq.index, uniq.values):

```

```

    if country in africa:
        african.update({country:pop})
    if not country == 'Nigeria':
        others.update({country:pop})

nonNGA = sum(others.values())
#print('Number of Non-Nigerian African Data Scientists:', nonNGA)

```

```

[13]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(5,2),facecolor='white')
ax = fig.add_subplot(1,1,1)

ax.text(1.0,1, "Key figures",color='black',fontsize=28, fontweight='bold',
↳fontfamily='monospace',ha='center')

ax.text(0, 0.4, f"{numNGA}",color='darkcyan',fontsize=25, fontweight='bold',
↳fontfamily='monospace',ha='center')
ax.text(0, 0.001, "out of 25973 \nrespondents are
↳Nigerian",color='dimgrey',fontsize=17, fontweight='light',
↳fontfamily='monospace',ha='center')

ax.text(1.0, 0.4, f"{perNGA}%",color='darkcyan',fontsize=25, fontweight='bold',
↳fontfamily='monospace',ha='center')
ax.text(1.0, 0.001, "of global respondents \nare
↳Nigerian",color='dimgrey',fontsize=17, fontweight='light',
↳fontfamily='monospace',ha='center')

ax.text(2.0, 0.4, f"{sum(african.values())}",color='darkcyan',fontsize=25,
↳fontweight='bold', fontfamily='monospace',ha='center')
ax.text(2.0, 0.001, "African \nData Scientists",color='dimgrey',fontsize=17,
↳fontweight='light', fontfamily='monospace',ha='center')

ax.text(0.5, -0.4, f"{round((numNGA/sum(african.values()))*100,
↳1)}%",color='darkcyan',fontsize=25, fontweight='bold',
↳fontfamily='monospace',ha='center')
ax.text(0.5, -0.75, "of African Data Scientists \nare Nigerian - A wide
↳margin",color='dimgrey',fontsize=17, fontweight='light',
↳fontfamily='monospace',ha='center')

ax.text(1.65, -0.4, f"{len(african)}",color='darkcyan',fontsize=25,
↳fontweight='bold', fontfamily='monospace',ha='center')
ax.text(1.65, -0.75, "African \nCountries
↳Represented",color='dimgrey',fontsize=17, fontweight='light',
↳fontfamily='monospace',ha='center')

```

```

ax.set_yticklabels('')
ax.tick_params(axis='y',length=0)
ax.tick_params(axis='x',length=0)
ax.set_xticklabels('')

for direction in ['top','right','left','bottom']:
    ax.spines[direction].set_visible(False)

```

Key figures


```
[14]: sns.set_theme()
```

```
[15]: color_lst = ['darkgray'] * 9
color_lst.insert(6, 'darkcyan')
```

```
[16]: plt.title('Top 10 Countries with the highest number of Data Scientists', weight_
↳='bold', fontsize = 15)
plots = uniq[:10].plot.bar(figsize=(16,10), color = color_lst)
annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[17]: color_lst2 = ['darkgray'] * 9
color_lst2.insert(0, 'darkcyan')
```

```
[18]: data = [[i[0], i[1]] for i in african.items()]

plots = pd.DataFrame(data, columns = ['Country', 'Number of Respondents']).plot.
↳ bar(x = 'Country', y = 'Number of Respondents', label = 'Highest_
↳ Representation', figsize=(16,10), color = color_lst2)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.xlabel('Country', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.title('African Countries with the Highest Representation in Data_
↳ Science\n', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
annot_bar(plots)
```

African Countries with the Highest Representation in Data Science


```
[19]: plt.figure(figsize = (20,10))
plt.title('Proportion of Global Respondent Data Scientists', weight = 'bold',
↳ fontsize = 15)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondent', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plots = sns.barplot(x = ['Nigeria', 'Rest of Africa', 'Rest of the World'], y =
↳ [numNGA, nonNGA, numRES - (numNGA + nonNGA)], palette = ['darkcyan',
↳ 'darkgrey', 'darkgrey'])

annot_bar(plots)
```


Based on Recent Growth Pattern, Nigeria is projected to be Top 3 by 2032

```
[20]: class suppress_stdout_stderr(object):
    """
    A context manager for doing a "deep suppression" of stdout and stderr in
    Python, i.e. will suppress all print, even if the print originates in a
    compiled C/Fortran sub-function.
    This will not suppress raised exceptions, since exceptions are printed
    to stderr just before a script exits, and after the context manager has
    exited (at least, I think that is why it lets exceptions through).
    """
    def __init__(self):
        # Open a pair of null files
        self.null_fds = [os.open(os.devnull, os.O_RDWR) for x in range(2)]
        # Save the actual stdout (1) and stderr (2) file descriptors.
        self.save_fds = (os.dup(1), os.dup(2))

    def __enter__(self):
        # Assign the null pointers to stdout and stderr.
        os.dup2(self.null_fds[0], 1)
        os.dup2(self.null_fds[1], 2)

    def __exit__(self, *_):
        # Re-assign the real stdout/stderr back to (1) and (2)
        os.dup2(self.save_fds[0], 1)
        os.dup2(self.save_fds[1], 2)
        # Close the null files
        os.close(self.null_fds[0])
```

```
os.close(self.null_fds[1])
```

```
[21]: Nigerians = {}

for date in [2017, 2018, 2019, 2020]:
    dpath = f'../input/kaggle-survey-{date}/'

    if date == 2019: MCQ = os.path.join(dpath, 'multiple_choice_responses.csv')
    elif date > 2019: MCQ = os.path.join(dpath, 'kaggle_survey_2020_responses.
↳ csv')
    else: MCQ = os.path.join(dpath, 'multipleChoiceResponses.csv')

    if dpath.endswith('2019/'): MCQ = MCQ.lower()

    surv = pd.read_csv(MCQ, error_bad_lines=False, warn_bad_lines=True,
↳ encoding='latin-1')

    try: Nigerians.update({date : len(surv[surv.Q3 == 'Nigeria'])})
    except: Nigerians.update({date : len(surv[surv['Country'] == 'Nigeria'])})

Nigerians.update({2021 : numNGA})
begin, end = 2022, 2033

X_test = [[i] for i in range(begin, end, )]
#y_pred = LinearRegression().fit(np.asarray(list(Nigerians.keys()))).
↳ reshape(-1,1), np.asarray(list(Nigerians.values()))).predict(X_test)

with suppress_stdout_stderr():
    y_pred = Prophet().fit(pd.DataFrame([Nigerians.keys(), Nigerians.
↳ values()],).T.rename( columns = {0 : 'ds', 1 : 'y'}), verbose = 1).
↳ predict(pd.DataFrame(X_test).rename(columns = {0 : 'ds'})).yhat

[Nigerians.update({k:v}) for k, v in zip(list(range(begin,end)), y_pred)]

years = pd.DataFrame(Nigerians, index = [0]).T
years.rename(columns = {0:'Number of Respondents'}, inplace=True)

plt.figure(figsize = (20,10))
```

```

plots = sns.barplot(x = years.index, y = years.values.reshape(1,-1)[0], palette_
↳ ([ 'darkgray' ] * 5 + [ 'darkcyan' ] * ( len(Nigerians) - 6 ) + [ 'brown' ] ))
plt.legend([ 'Darkgray - Recent Years', 'Darkcyan - Predicted Years before Top_
↳ Three Entry', 'Brown - Year of Top Three Entry' ])
label_plot('Number of Nigerian Respondents by Year', x = 'Years', y = 'Number_
↳ of Respondents')
annot_bar(plots)

```



```

[22]: Japan = {}

for date in [2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021]:
    dpath = f'../input/kaggle-survey-{date}/'

    if dpath.endswith('2019/'): MCQ = os.path.join(dpath,
↳ 'multiple_choice_responses.csv')
    elif dpath.endswith('2020/') or dpath.endswith('2021/'): MCQ = os.path.
↳ join(dpath, f'kaggle_survey_{date}_responses.csv')
    else: MCQ = os.path.join(dpath, 'multipleChoiceResponses.csv')

    if dpath.endswith('2019/'): MCQ = MCQ.lower()

    surv = pd.read_csv(MCQ, error_bad_lines=False, warn_bad_lines=True,
↳ encoding='latin-1')

    try: Japan.update({date : len(surv[surv.Q3 == 'Japan'])})
    except: Japan.update({date : len(surv[surv['Country'] == 'Japan'])})

```

```

X_test = [[i] for i in range(begin, end)]
#y_pred = LinearRegression().fit(np.asarray(list(Japan.keys()))).
↳reshape(-1,1), np.asarray(list(Japan.values()))).predict(X_test)

with suppress_stdout_stderr():
    y_pred = Prophet().fit(pd.DataFrame([Japan.keys(), Japan.values()],).T.
↳rename( columns = {0 : 'ds', 1 : 'y'}), verbose = 1).predict(pd.
↳DataFrame(X_test).rename(columns = {0 : 'ds'})).yhat

[Japan.update({k:v}) for k, v in zip(list(range(begin,end)), y_pred)]

jyears = pd.DataFrame(Japan, index = [0]).T
jyears.rename(columns = {0:'Number of Respondents'}, inplace=True)

plt.figure(figsize = (20,10))
plots = sns.barplot(x = jyears.index, y = jyears.values.reshape(1,-1)[0],
↳palette = (['darkgray']*5 + ['darkcyan'] * (len(Japan)-6) + ['darkorange']))
plt.legend(['Darkgray - Recent Years', 'Darkcyan - Predicted Years before Top
↳Three Departure', 'Brown - Year of Top Three Departure'])
label_plot('Number of Japanese Respondents by Year', x = 'Years', y = 'Number
↳of Respondents')
annot_bar(plots)

```



```
[23]: plt.figure(figsize=(16,6))
plt.plot(years.index, years.values.reshape(1,-1)[0])
plt.plot(jyears.index, jyears.values.reshape(1,-1)[0])
label_plot('Expected Growth of Data Scientist Population between Nigeria and Japan', x = 'Years', y = 'Number of Respondents')
plt.legend(['NIGERIA', 'JAPAN (3rd highest Number of Respondents)'], loc = 7)
```

[23]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x7fdfef6cd910>

Facts about Nigeria's Data Scientists

```
[24]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('Age Distribution', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents\n', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.xlabel('\nAge Bins (years)', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plots = NGA['Q1'].value_counts().plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')
annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[25]: plot_donut(NGA, 'Q2', 'Gender Distribution')
```

Gender Distribution


```
[26]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('Employment Status', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.xlabel('Role', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plots = NGA['Q5'].value_counts().plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')
annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[27]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('Years of experience in coding', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 17)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
plt.xlabel('Duration (years)', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
plots = NGA['Q6'].value_counts().plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')
annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[28]: plt.title('Highest Educational Level', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 17)
plt.ylabel('Educational Level', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
plt.xlabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
NGA['Q4'].value_counts().plot.barh(figsize=(20, 10), color = 'darkcyan')
plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
```



```
[29]: Q18col = [f'Q18_Part_{i}' for i in range(1,7)] + ['Q18_OTHER']
Q18 = NGA[Q18col]
Q18agg = Q18[~ Q18.isna()].stack()
```

```
plot_donut(Q18agg, title = "Most Utilised Computer Vision Method\n")
```

Most Utilised Computer Vision Method


```
[30]: Q19col = [f'Q19_Part_{i}' for i in range(1,6)] + ['Q19_OTHER']
Q19 = NGA[Q19col]
Q19agg = Q19[~ Q19.isna()].stack()
```

```
plot_donut(Q19agg, title = "Most Utilised Natural Language Processing (NLP)\n↳Methods\n", figsize = (8,8))
```

Most Utilised Natural Language Processing (NLP) Methods


```
[31]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('Distribution of yearly Compensation', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 17)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
plt.xlabel('Amount (USD - $)', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
plots = NGA['Q25'].value_counts().plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')
annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[32]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('First Language to learn for Data Science', weight = 'bold', fontsize=15)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.xlabel('Programming Language', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plots = NGA['Q8'].value_counts().plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')

annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[33]: #plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
#plt.title('Computing device used for programming', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 17)
#plt.xlabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
#plt.ylabel('Device', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
#NGA['Q11'].value_counts().plot.barh(color = 'darkcyan')
#plt.gca().invert_yaxis()

plot_donut(NGA, 'Q11', 'Computing Device Used for Programming', explode = [0, 0.05, 0.04, 0.5, 0.75])
```

Computing Device Used for Programming


```
[34]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('Amount spent on Machine Learning or Cloud Computing services', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.xlabel('Amount (USD - $)', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plots = NGA['Q25'].value_counts().plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')
annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[35]: Q9col = [f'Q9_Part_{i}' for i in range(1,13)] + ['Q9_OTHER']
Q9 = NGA[Q9col]
Q9agg = Q9[~ Q9.isna()].stack()
#Q9agg = Q9agg.drop(0, 0)

label_plot("Most Utilised Integrated Development Environment (IDE)\n\n",
↳"IDEs", "Number of Respondents")
plots = plot_bar(Q9agg)
plt.text(-0.5, 460, 'Note: Some respondents chose categories more than once',
↳fontSize = 20, color = 'green')
annot_bar(plots)
```

Most Utilised Integrated Development Environment (IDE)


```
[36]: Q10col = [f'Q10_Part_{i}' for i in range(1,17)] + ['Q10_OTHER']
Q10 = NGA[Q10col]
Q10agg = Q10[~ Q10.isna()].stack()
```

```

label_plot("Most Utilised Hosted Notebook Products\n\n", "Notebook Product",
↳"Number of Respondents")
plots = plot_bar(Q10agg)
#plt.text(-0.5, 275, 'Note: Some respondents chose more than one category',
↳fontsize = 20, color = 'green')
annot_bar(plots)

```

Most Utilised Hosted Notebook Products


```

[37]: #Data preprocessing
Q12col = [f'Q12_Part_{i}' for i in range(1,6)] + ['Q12_OTHER']
Q12 = NGA[Q12col]
Q12agg = Q12[~ Q12.isna()].stack()

#Donut plot
plot_donut(Q12agg, title = "Most Utilised Specialized Hardware\n")

```

Most Utilised Specialized Hardware


```
[38]: Q17col = [f'Q17_Part_{i}' for i in range(1,12)] + ['Q17_OTHER']
Q17 = NGA[Q17col]
Q17agg = Q17[~ Q17.isna()].stack()

label_plot("Most Utilised Machine Learning Algorithms\n", "Number of
↳ Respondents", "Algorithm")
plots = plot_bar(Q17agg, horizontal = True)
```



```
[39]: Q14col = [f'Q14_Part_{i}' for i in range(1,12)] + ['Q14_OTHER']
Q14 = NGA[Q14col]
Q14agg = Q14[~ Q14.isna()].stack()
```

```
label_plot("Most Utilised Data Visualization Libraries or Tools\n", "Library / Tool", "Number of Respondents")
plots = plot_bar(Q14agg)
annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[40]: Q16col = [f'Q16_Part_{i}' for i in range(1,18)] + ['Q16_OTHER']
Q16 = NGA[Q16col]
Q16agg = Q16[~ Q16.isna()].stack()

label_plot("Most Utilised Machine Learning Frameworks\n", "Framework", "Number_
of Respondents")
plots = plot_bar(Q16agg)
annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[41]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('Best Cloud platform with Developer Experience', weight = 'bold',
fontsize = 15)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.xlabel('Cloud Platform', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plots = NGA['Q28'].value_counts()[1:-1].plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')

annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[42]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('Distribution of most often used Big Data Products', weight = 'bold',
↪      ↪fontsize = 15)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.xlabel('Product', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plots = NGA['Q33'].value_counts().plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')

annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[43]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('Most used Business Intelligence tool', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.xlabel('Business Intelligence tool', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plots = NGA['Q35'].value_counts().plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')

annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[44]: #plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
#plt.title('Primary tool for analysis', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 17)
#plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
#plt.xlabel('Business Intelligence tool', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
#plots = NGA['Q41'].value_counts().plot.barh(color = 'darkcyan')
#plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
#annot_bar(plots)

plot_donut(NGA, 'Q41', 'Primary Tool for Analysis', explode = [0, 0, 0.05, 0.
↪04, 0.03, 0.01])
```

Primary Tool for Analysis


```
[45]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('Number of times a TPU has been used', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.xlabel('Number of Times', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plots = NGA['Q13'].value_counts().plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')

annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[46]: Q42col = [f'Q42_Part_{i}' for i in range(1,12)] + ['Q42_OTHER']
Q42 = NGA[Q42col]
Q42agg = Q42[~ Q42.isna()].stack()
```

```
label_plot("Favourite Media that post Data Science Contents", 'Number of Respondents', 'Platforms')
plots = plot_bar(Q42agg, horizontal = True)
```



```
[47]: Q39col = [f'Q39_Part_{i}' for i in range(1,10)] + ['Q39_OTHER']
Q39 = NGA[Q39col]
Q39agg = Q39[~ Q39.isna()].stack()
```

```
label_plot("Most Utilised Platforms for Publicly Sharing of\nData Analysis or Machine Learning Applications", 'Number of Respondents', 'Platforms')
plots = plot_bar(Q39agg, horizontal = True)
```



```
[48]: Q40col = [f'Q40_Part_{i}' for i in range(1,12)] + ['Q40_OTHER']
Q40 = NGA[Q40col]
Q40agg = Q40[~ Q40.isna()].stack()

label_plot("Platforms Where Data Science Courses Were Begun or Completed",
           'Number of Respondents', 'Platforms')
plots = plot_bar(Q40agg, horizontal = True)
```



```
[49]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('Number of years spent using Machine Learning methods', weight = 'bold',
         ↪ 'bold', fontsize = 15)
```

```
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.xlabel('Duration (years)', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plots = NGA['Q15'].value_counts().plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')
annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[50]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('Industry of current employment', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.xlabel('Industry', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plots = NGA['Q20'].value_counts().plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')
annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[51]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('Size of company of employment', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.xlabel('Number of employees', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plots = NGA['Q21'].value_counts().plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')
annot_bar(plots)
```



```
[52]: plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
plt.title('Number of Individuals responsible for Data Workload in businesses',
         weight = 'bold', fontsize = 15)
plt.ylabel('Number of Respondents', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plt.xlabel('Number of Individuals', weight = 'bold', fontsize = 13)
plots = NGA['Q22'].value_counts().plot.bar(color = 'darkcyan')
annot_bar(plots)
```


0.2 Conclusion

Important things to check out *Source: African Economic Merit Awards - Tech. in Nigeria*

- [AI Readiness in Nigeria](#)
- [Keyword Trends on Data Science in Nigeria](#)
- [Open Source Contribution in Nigeria](#)

Note: > An extra parameter I would've really loved to work on, would've been details on the traditional educational discipline of respondents, which would've been useful in assessing the proportion of those who pivoted from non-tech backgrounds.

I'm sure it would be a significant percentage, there's a tech. revolution coming in Nigeria.

0.2.1 Let's Connect

Author: [Alao David I.](#)

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